

Ontology-based Modelling and Reasoning for Forest Fire Emergencies in Resilient Societies

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Every year, thousands of forest fires throughout the world cause disasters. One of the most critical challenges during a wildfire disaster is the effective management of heterogeneous information relative to the crisis to support human operators and authorities. Towards addressing this challenge, this paper presents an ontology-based framework for data representation and interlinking of wildfire events that are being used to foster advanced reasoning, situational awareness and interpretation for decision support. More specifically, we illustrate the capabilities of the ONTO-SAFE ontology to symbolically model contextual information in the domain, addressing application and user requirements promoting the creation of interoperable knowledge graphs. On top of the symbolic knowledge graphs, we define a rule-based framework for infusing expert knowledge in the form of constraints and rules to recognize patterns and situations of interest based on domain knowledge, assisting end-users in taking informed decisions and facilitating advanced decision-making.

CCS CONCEPTS • Ontology • Semantic Web • Semantic Reasoning

Additional Keywords and Phrases: Forest Fires, Decision Support

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1 INTRODUCTION

Climate change, which has been identified as one of the most serious concerns confronting humanity, has intensified the climate risks and increased the probability of extreme weather disasters, such as forest fires [1]. Consequently, the large number of forest fires has posed severe short and long-term effects on the environment, economic growth and development. The consequences of natural disasters provoke enormous challenges not only to the general public but also to the disaster management teams or emergency response units responsible for managing disaster responses [2]. In order to mitigate the challenges and help society in becoming more resilient, several research actions are initialized that involve the combination and integration of several technologies into forest fire emergency management systems [3].

In this context, several attempts have been made to enhance the forest fire detection accuracy and provide the tools necessary to help the society becoming more resilient, safe and sustainable in the wildfire hazard context, by providing an integrated solution featuring a forest fire Decision Support System. For example, the combination of novel technologies, such as the use of earth observations from Copernicus and GEOSS based on the use of sensors and indirect sensing methods that involve crowdsourced data from social media and chatbot, constitutes a critical aspect in emergency management processing [4]. In this quest, Semantic Web technologies are utilized to represent knowledge and data sources, as well as generate rich knowledge graphs and support forest fire stakeholders in decision making by using contextual information, such as weather forecast, location of hotspots, type of smoke, number of people at risk, etc.

This paper describes ONTO-SAFE, a lightweight framework for capturing and interlinking heterogeneous data collected from several resources such as environmental, sensors, social media, input from first responders and/or people in danger and to semantically integrate them in order to provide decision support services to the crisis management center. To achieve interoperability at different levels, we use OWL 2 ontologies [5] as the underlying knowledge representation formalism, generating interoperable Knowledge Graphs (KGs) that are aligned with existing vocabularies and conceptual models, such as SoKNOS [6] and BeAWARE [7]. The symbolic knowledge is further enriched with rules to derive logical consequences and semantically enrich the KGs, aiming at improving all phases of forest fire emergency management, where all actors involved in the management cycle (decision makers, in-field agents, volunteers and citizens) can effectively cooperate.

The contribution of our work can be summarized in the following:

- We reuse and combine different ontologies in a structural and modular manner to define the conceptual model of the underlying KGs at different levels. Capitalizing on existing modelling standards (OWL 2 ontologies) and recommendations, our framework supports the aggregated representation of wildfire and relevant incidents and impacts, data from human and earth observations, missions and relationships between the services, higher level knowledge and user-centered information to facilitate intelligent interlinking that can be easily shared and used inside rules
- We use the latest W3C recommendation (SHACL) [8] for encoding domain knowledge and monitoring patterns, defining the logic to monitor situations of interests.
- We demonstrate use cases with real-world data and showcase the way our framework supports the different stakeholders.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents related work on ontologies related to crisis, emergency management and disaster planning. In Section 3, the ONTO-SAFE framework with the architecture and the functionalities is presented. Section 4 presents the ontology along with how it was conceptualized in order to meet user

requirements, as Section 5 describes the reasoning module for decision support. Finally, Section 6 concludes this work and reports possible future steps.

2 RELATED WORK

Managing complex situations during an emergency event, such as wildfire, is a difficult challenge because of the coordination of all relevant stakeholders involved and the vital nature of the event itself [9]. Difficulties in communication and uncertainties may arise as a result of a wide range of heterogeneous information generated from different systems and diverse terminology used by Emergency Responders (ERs) [10]. Semantic web technologies attempt to address these issues, through the conceptualization of the knowledge via ontologies and the ability to conveniently access data using semantic queries, which is a major benefit of semantic representation and disseminating data on the web.

SoKNOS [6] is an integrated emergency management system that allows different uses of ontologies and semantic technologies to support the objective of a semantically unambiguous and shared information foundation across organizations. The central ontology of SoKNOS system is central domain ontology for emergency management that focuses on establishing a hierarchical framework of material and human resources to improve the availability of the right information at the right time. Additional ontologies are used to describe resources and damages, as well as deployment regulations that define the relationships between resources and damages.

In addition, Empathi [11] ontology conceptualizes the key principles that describe the domain of emergency management and disaster planning. This ontology is used to automatically recognize incidents during emergency and disaster concepts generated by social media conversations, allowing law enforcement agencies to track events in real-time. The ontology was built using the semantic web language (OWL) and includes links to other important ontologies such as FOAF, SIOC, DC-terms, and LOD. Empathi ontology is used for semantic annotation using expanded concepts. For instance, in order to identify useful information from unstructured social media material and to classify messages as relevant or irrelevant to a crisis, Empathi ontology maps the words to ontology classes and improves the understanding of these messages in order to enhance the knowledge in the crisis management domain.

Another highly relevant approach is EmergencyFire [12] ontology. EmergencyFire is an ontology for describing emergency response protocols with the primary goal of improving information sharing and integration, in order to provide useful and common information between people and systems in the event of a building fire disaster. Emergency ontology is a component of a system in which a user enters information regarding an emergency situation and the application responds with the protocol that must be followed, such as actions to be executed and the engaged organizations and resources. In this way, the interoperability provided by the EmergencyFire ontology improves response time in emergency scenarios while eliminating false compliances.

Furthermore, BeAWARE [7] ontology is a lightweight knowledge representation model for semantic representation of concepts involved in climate-related crisis management. The BeAWARE ontology presents a comprehensive model for semantically representing: a) climate-related natural disasters (floods, earthquakes, forest fires etc.), b) multimodal sensor data analysis and c) rescue unit assignments. This ontology combines heterogeneous data produced from a crisis representation, such as climate parameters that may trigger climate crises, data from sensor analysis and social media inputs, in order to support decision-making in climate crisis scenarios. All this information is converted to operational missions and first responder unit assignments.

In the area of wildfires, Kalabokidis et al. [13] also describe an ontology-based geoportal that depends on semantic relationships between resources. The OntoFire system makes use of domain ontology for wildfires that semantically

organizes the metadata presented at this portal. The relationships that connect semantically relevant pieces of information can be used to find correlations between different types of data and generate useful information. With this technique, the system may be enhanced with additional semantically annotated metadata descriptions, which will contribute to knowledge dissemination and operational stakeholder preparedness in natural disasters.

Overall, since the existing ontology-based approaches only cover a subset of semantically representing crisis management and forest fire emergency situations, the proposed ONTO-SAFE ontology-based approach consists of modules for representing all aspects of forest fire management in all phases of the Disaster Risk Management cycle adopting concepts from some of the existing ontologies as well, predominantly from BeAWARE and SoKNOS.

3 ONTO-SAFE FRAMEWORK

One of the main objectives of the ONTO-SAFE framework is to provide the semantic reasoning framework that analyzes data to provide relevant alerts and high-level recommendations to users based on the respective phase of DRS cycle (preparedness, response, recovery) and also considering their location. Reasoning is performed on top of the ONTO-SAFE domain ontology that aims at inferring underlying knowledge and discovering connections between ontology entities during incidents that occur before, during and after wildfires. In particular, the reasoning module is responsible for deriving new facts and relationships based on the existing knowledge captured in the knowledge base repository. The ONTO-SAFE framework has been implemented as part of the Knowledge Base Service and runs on top of the ONTO-SAFE ontology.

Figure 1 Architecture of ONTO-SAFE's framework

Figure 1 presents the internal architecture of the ONTO-SAFE framework consisting of the following parts:

- **Ontology**, which contains the formal representation of the information such as the types, properties, and inter-relationships of different entities

- **Knowledge Base Repository (KBR)**, which hosts the ontology and also offers native RDF storage and querying services
- **Knowledge Base Population (KBP)**, which implements the mechanisms for mapping input retrieved from intelligent services
- **Semantic Reasoning**, which implements the reasoning framework combining native OWL2 reasoning, SHACL rules, etc. and provides the relevant alerts to users.
- **Knowledge Base Service (KBS)**, which is the central component of the system architecture since it is the main interface to the ONTO-SAFE ontology.

In this way, the Knowledge Base Service accepts analysis results from other components and integrates them semantically into the ontology. Furthermore, this service manages the output of the semantic reasoning process and sends the inferred, high-level information to other system components that are interested. In this paper, we focus mainly on Ontology (Section 4) and Semantic Reasoning (Section 5).

4 ONTO-SAFE ONTOLOGY CONCEPTUALIZATION

During forest fire situations, adequate situational awareness information is crucial in the domain of emergency management. In addition, as forest fires threaten human lives and property, the need for analytical best practice tools to assist forest fire managers in evaluating alternatives and making decisions is expanding. To improve the fire safety of our communities, organize better the emergency management operation and restore the health and resilience of forests, grasslands and natural places, emergency management best practices are applied in all forest fire disaster phases and help to develop a resilience action plan in forests. The ONTO-SAFE ontology's major aim is to give an effective conceptualization of existing data and to build a new knowledge base based on existing best practices in wildfire emergency management.

The involvement of end-users in the development of the ONTO-SAFE ontology is considered very useful, as it allows us to collect a deeper knowledge of end-users needs and expectations. Furthermore, requirements were defined and prioritized through the online survey and the International User Requirements Workshop (IURW), which are the two methodologies deployed so far to collect the preliminary inputs from the end-users (i.e., wildfire managers). Table 1 contains an indicative subset of the user requirements.

Table 1 Subset of the User Requirements

User Requirement ID	Description	Phase of the emergency
REQ-10	Get the weather forecasts daily, weekly and monthly	Prevention & Preparedness
REQ-30	Classify the type of smoke column	Detection & Response
REQ-89	Make a comparison between pre-fire and post-fire landscape structure for calculation of severity indexes	Adaption & Restoration

Moreover, the definition of important entities, concepts, and procedures is critical for managing hazardous situations during wildfires. For this reason, the ontology generates a conceptual map of organizing elements inside a domain utilizing classes, properties, and instances to facilitate data modelling, integration, and reasoning over the resulting information. This approach focuses on current and future needs across the three different phases of wildfire management,

prevention & preparedness, detection & response, and adaptation & restoration. Depending on the phase of the wildfire management cycle, relevant results will be generated.

In other words, the ontology is the knowledge representation model for semantically representing notions pertinent to the project by capturing the results of the analysis modules in a reusable and interoperable way. The ontology-based approach consists of modules for representing all aspects of forest fire management in all phases of the Disaster Risk Management (DRM) cycle, adopting concepts from some of the existing ontologies, and delivers a more holistic, all-around model for semantically representing:

- Relevant incidents and impacts in a wildfire disaster and associated weather conditions
- Data coming from human and earth observations
- Missions and relationships between the services

In addition, in order to properly construct the ontology and reach the requirements from users, the ontology was assessed efficiently via competency questions.

4.1 Competency Questions

Competency Questions (CQs) are a set of natural language questions that must be answered correctly by the ontology and they are crucial in the ontology development process since they represent ontology needs [14]. A competency question is a natural language sentence that specifies a pattern for the type of question that ontology should be able to answer. As a result, the ontology's answerability of CQs becomes a functional requirement. Based on the aforementioned list of user needs, the ontology can respond to a variety of CQs, such as representing a wildfire incident (e.g., location, weather variables for this location) or locating affected people. In ONTO-SAFE, competency questions cover semantically three core aspects that served as the foundation for the design of the ontology: (a) relevant incidents and impacts in a wildfire disaster and associated weather conditions, (b) data coming from human and earth observations, and, (c) missions and relationships between the services. Table 2 shows how the user requirements were initially mapped to ontology's CQs.

Table 2 User requirements mapping to CQs

Representation of wildfire disaster and relevant incidents and impacts
CQ1. What are the most important weather variables that can cause forest fire?
CQ2. What are the current measurements for these weather variables?
CQ3. What is the forecast for the weather in this location?
CQ4. Where did the incident take place?
CQ5. What is the priority of an incident during a forest fire disaster?
CQ6. What incidents during forest fires are the most urgent?
Representation of data from human and earth observations
CQ7. What data from the source are depicted?
CQ8. Which is the creation date of these data?
CQ9. What is the location of this item?
CQ10. Which is the classification type of smoke?
CQ11. Which vulnerable objects were involved in the incident?
CQ12. What is the status of wildfire forestry works (firebreaks, access to forest roads, etc.)?

Representation of missions and relationships between the services

- CQ13. What services or support do you offer for firefighting?
 - CQ14. Which mission do you follow for this support/service?
 - CQ15. What is the location where this mission is taking place?
 - CQ16. Where is the most urgent mission taking place?
 - CQ17. What is the population density in the area?
 - CQ18. What is the location of the involved people?
-

4.2 Representation of wildfire and relevant incidents and impacts

Starting with the representation of wildfire disasters and relevant incidents and impacts, we represent the most important classes, as illustrated in Figure 2. Class Fire represents the various types of fires, e.g. forest fire, land fire or urban fire, etc. Fires may lead to other fires (via property leads to). For instance, a forest fire may lead to land fire, or an urban fire may lead to a forest fire. Each type of fire starts/ends at a specific time and is characterized by a location, represented via class Location, which represents a location (point or area), indicated by latitude and longitude. Furthermore, fire has an impact (via class Impact), which can represent injuries, deaths, destroyed houses, cars, etc., and also be related to an incident (via class Incident). Furthermore, we used SoKNOS ontology [6] for categorizing types of damages and resources and the relations between them. In addition, every location has specific climate conditions, which are represented via class WeatherConditionParameter with specific information and values (e.g. temperature, wind speed, humidity), and a weather forecast (via class WeatherForecast). To understand better the usage of the classes and properties and how this construction can be linked to the project's real needs we present the following scenario, which took place in Greece's forest, in the location Mati in 2018 [15]. Figure 2 presents this information.

Figure 2 Representation of incidents and impacts at a specific scenario

4.3 Representation of data from human and earth observations

Aside from representing wildfire disasters and relevant incidents and impacts, the ONTO-SAFE ontology also includes data relevant to the analysis of input data coming from the framework's various sensors, satellites and social media

sources (Twitter, chatbot, etc.). This information is fed to the ontology from the analysis components and the Class `MediaItem` represents an item of analyzed data. Text, images, videos, and audio are all examples of media objects that were created during the crisis. Class `Observation` represents the observations made by sensors (via class `Sensor`) or by satellites (via class `Satellite`). Moreover, for describing sensors and their observations we based on SSN vocabulary [16] with a focus on what senses, how it senses, and what is sensed. The analysis of the respective items (text analysis, image analysis, video analysis, satellite analysis, or sensor analysis) produces a `Dataset` (via class `Dataset`) containing all relevant information about the media item, which is published by a `Stakeholder`. Classes `Dataset` and `MediaItem` were reused from the `beAWARE` ontology [7], which is a lightweight knowledge representation model for semantic representation of concepts involved in climate-related crisis management. Thus, datasets can produce alerts (via class `Alert`), early warning and risk maps and contain fire detection (via class `Detection`). All this information is given to the ontology through various components. The ontology's main constructs for this analysis are depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Representation of data from human observation

4.4 Representation of missions and relationships between the services

The third component of the ontology is responsible for semantically representing missions and relationships between the services. All stakeholders (class `Stakeholder`) have been assigned to one or more missions (class `Mission`), which relate to incidents that involve participating entities (class `HighlyVulnerableObject`). A mission is also characterized by start and end time, status, mission priority and mission status. A `HighlyVulnerableObject` is characterized by status and can be assets, like infrastructure and property or living being, like animal and human. Also, stakeholders probably travel with vehicle (class `Vehicle`), which in turn belong to a department (class `Department`). Any vehicle has a status and coordinates (longitude, latitude) in order to know better the vehicle's location and the status of this. Furthermore, if the stakeholders are professionals, they belong or lead a team (class `Team`) and work for a department (class `Department`). Figure 4 depicts these relationships.

Figure 4 Representation of relationships between the services

5 REASONING MODULE FOR DECISION SUPPORT

5.1 Data Integration

Semantic integration mechanisms are developed, in order to add to the ontology information that derives from different analysis components. These mechanisms taking into account the data generated by intelligent services and derived from different sources such as earth observations from the Copernicus Sentinels and GEOSS, wildfire sensors in forests, topographic data, weather forecasts and even crowdsourced data from social media and other applications that can be used by citizens and first responders to provide situational in-field information. In addition, the reasoning scheme is based on SHACL-compliant rules and is responsible for deriving new facts and relationships based on the existing knowledge captured in the knowledge base repository.

More specifically, KBS component receives data through message bus, which is the means of communication and allows the exchange of messages. These messages are received in NetCDF [17] or JSON format from the relevant component and analyzed by the KBS. Analyzed data are semantically integrated into the appropriate classes considering the ontology, as data acquired from various system components (e.g. weather forecasts, chatbots, sensors, etc.) are stored in the ontology. Data transformation is carried out from the KBP component, which is responsible for the promotion of research into discovering facts about entities and adding this information to the ontology. Below are some examples of how to express domain concepts in RDF format. The first example in Table 3, shows the Report of fire, which receives via chatbot application, and takes place in a specific Location. Chatbot is a module capable of gathering information about wildfire events and delivering a summarized report of the event's impact to decision-makers. Reports may include other Media items such as images, videos, etc.

Table 3 RDF representation of a Report of fire

```

<rdf:Description rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/sf#Report_1">
  <rdf:type rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/sf#Report"/>
  <sf:hasTimestamp rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#dateTime">
    2021-11-26T13:55:00.000+02:00</sf:hasTimestamp>
  <sf:hasReportHazard>Fire</sf:hasReportHazard>
  <sf:hasReportStatus>Notified</sf:hasReportStatus>
  <sf:hasReportContent>Submitted</sf:hasReportContent>
  <sf:id>1</sf:id>
  <sf:hasDescription>Fire near house</sf:hasDescription>
  <sf:Source>Chatbot</sf:Source>
  <sf:hasLocation rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/sf#Location_142"/>
  <sf:hasMediaURI rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/sf#MediaURIs"/>
</rdf:Description>

```

Moreover, the second example in Table 4 shows the representation of a point with a weather forecast variable Fire Weather Index (FWI), which is a meteorologically based index that is used to estimate fire danger [18]. FWI is made up of various components that take into account the effects of fuel moisture and wind on fire behavior and spread.

Table 4 RDF representation of Point

```

<rdf:Description rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/sf#Point_01c95">
  <rdf:type>ogc:Geometry</rdf:type>
  <rdf:type rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/sf#Weatherpoint"/>
  <sf:hasWeatherCondition rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/sf#WeatherConditionParameter_7284"/>
  <sf:hasLatitude>40.551008</sf:hasLatitude>
  <sf:hasLongitude>22.712769</sf:hasLongitude>
  <sf:hasFWI>32.2</sf:hasFWI>
  <sf:hasTimestamp>2021-08-14T00:00:00
</sf:hasTimestamp>
  <ogc:asWKT><http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/1.3/CRS84>
    POINT(40.551008 22.712769)^ogc:wktLiteral</ogc:asWKT>
</rdf:Description>

```

Weather conditions parameters are provided for any moment of time and for every point in the specific location. More specifically, weather conditions are responsible for fire danger, if the value of these exceeds the desired limits, and demonstrates the possibility of fire. The example above includes the FWI in a specific location and we can identify that central concepts of the ONTO-SAFE ontology WeatherConditionParameter and Location, via latitude and longitude, are represented.

In addition, KBS component retrieves this information and converts it to meaningful message. This message contains useful information regarding the incident, which takes place in the specific location and gives the user the relevant information, such as alerts or recommendations, in order to act accordingly in a crisis situation.

The following example in Table 5 depicts the structure of alert that derives from the KBS component when the weather variable FWI exceeds the desired limits¹ and the situation is characterized by “Extreme”, in order to inform the decision-makers and first responders and act accordingly. The alert includes the timestamp of this event, the status,

¹ <https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/about-effis/technical-background/fire-danger-forecast>

source, scope, some information regarding the category, urgency, severity, certainty, the exact point where the event takes place and the communication message with description, in order to understand better stakeholders the meaning of this alert.

Table 5 The structure of the alert generated from semantic reasoning

```
{
  "identifier":"identifier",
  "sender":"SEM",
  "sent":"2021-08-27T11:35:26+02:00",
  "status":"Actual",
  "msgType":"Alert",
  "source":"EFFIS_FWI",
  "scope":"Public",
  "code":[ ],
  "info":{
    "category":"Met",
    "event":"Probability of fire",
    "urgency":"Immediate",
    "severity":" Moderate",
    "certainty":"Likely",
    "description":"Create a safety zone of up to 100 feet around your home. Remove pine needles and
dry leaves from around your home. Keep woodpiles at least 30 feet from your home.",
    "area":{
      "point":"40.6347640 23.0546899"
    }
  }
}
```

6 RULE-BASED REASONING

Knowledge Base Service (KBS) includes a semantic reasoning mechanism to infer implicit knowledge from explicitly asserted facts existing in the ontology and detect connections between ontology notions. The reasoning mechanism has been implemented as a set of connected SHACL queries that traverse the KB and return information, which is then added back to the KB. More specifically, this mechanism is responsible for searching incoming data during a wildfire event and handles their semantic representation and integration into the ontology, in order to form a unified reasoning process. The queries were created in order to answer useful information and more specifically to transform the list of CQs into SHACL queries. Table 6 shows an example of a set of CQs and their SHACL translations.

Table 6 An indicative set of CQs along with their SHACL translation.

Competency Question	SHACL query
What are the current measurements for weather variables that can cause forest fire in specific location?	<pre>ex:MeasurementShape a sh:NodeShape ; sh:severity sh:Info ; sh:targetClass sf:Measurement ; sh:sparql [sh:message "Measurement of variable in specific location" ; sh:select "" SELECT ?location \$this WHERE {</pre>

Competency Question	SHACL query
Which is the classification type of smoke?	<pre> ?location sf:hasGeometry ?point. ?point rdf:type sf:Weatherpoint. ?point sf:hasWeatherCondition ?condition. ?condition sf:hasWeatherConditionMeasurement \$this. }""";]. ex:ClassificationShape a sh:NodeShape ; sh:severity sh:Info ; sh:targetClass sf:Classification ; sh:sparql [sh:message "Classification type of smoke" ; sh:select "" SELECT ?incident \$this ?type WHERE { ?incident rdf:type sf:Incident. ?incident sf:hasDetection ?detection. ?detection sf:hasClassification \$this. \$this sf:hasClassificationType ?type. }""";] . </pre>
What is the location where this mission is taking place?	<pre> ex:LocationShape a sh:NodeShape ; sh:severity sh:Info ; sh:targetClass sf:Location ; sh:sparql [sh:message "Location where this mission is taking place" ; sh:select "" SELECT ?mission \$this WHERE { ?mission rdf:type sf:Mission. \$this rdf:type sf:Location. ?mission sf:hasMissionLocation \$this. }""";] . </pre>

Moreover, the semantic reasoning component is able to extract additional information of wildfire incident related to each location, such as the nearest hospital, the nearest water source from the fire, etc. Using geospatial data, which is modelled using GeoSPARQL [19], enriches the wildfire incident information with geolocation information as detecting the potential number of hospitals (Table 7) or other critical infrastructure, in the area of interest. The query (Table 8) further detects the nearest water source from the fire incident. This information can be used by the decision-makers to assist them to come to a decision and create the respective missions in order to provide support to these areas. The following tables (Table 7 and Table 8) represent a subset of geolocation CQs along with their SHACL translation.

Table 7 Which is the nearest hospital?

```

ex:HospitalShape
a sh:NodeShape ;
sh:severity sh:Info ;
sh:targetClass sf:Hospital ;
sh:sparql [
  sh:message "Nearest hospital from fire" ;
  sh:select ""SELECT $this WHERE {
?alert rdf:type sf:AlertReport ;
ogc:asWKT point1;
sf:id ?alert_id.
$this rdf:type sf:Hospital ;
ogc:asWKT point2;
sf:hospital_id ?hospital_id.
BIND (geof:distance(?point1, ?point2, uom:metre) AS ?distance) .
} ORDER BY ASC(?distance)
LIMIT 1"";] .

```

Table 8 Where is the nearest water source from the fire?

```

ex:WaterSourceShape
a sh:NodeShape ;
sh:severity sh:Info ;
sh:targetClass sf:WaterSource ;
sh:sparql [
  sh:message "Nearest water source from fire" ;
  sh:select ""SELECT $this WHERE {
?alert rdf:type sf:AlertReport ;
ogc:asWKT point1;
sf:id ?alert_id.
$this rdf:type sf:WaterSource ;
ogc:asWKT point2;
sf:wsource_id ?wsource_id.
BIND (geof:distance(?point1, ?point2, uom:metre) AS ?distance) .
} ORDER BY ASC(?distance)
LIMIT 1"";] .

```

In cases that we want to detect a specific location where the sensor of camera detects a fire in this location, we combine information coming from in-situ cameras with decision-makers missions. More specifically, as presented in Table 9 the query searches among of incidents that correspond with the fire detection in the specific location. This query is running on GraphDB² that acts as the Knowledge Base Repository. Since the incident includes the detection of fire, the proper mission added in this incident and activated. Thus, the decision-makers can be able to send the suitable equipment to carry out this mission.

² <https://www.ontotext.com/products/graphdb/>

Table 9 Semantic Query to add mission in incident

```

INSERT{
  ?incident sf:relatesToMission ?mission .
  ?mission rdfs:subClassOf sf:Mission.
  ?mission rdf:type sf:DropWaterMission .
}
WHERE{
  ?incident rdf:type sf:Incident.
  ?incident sf:relatesToMission ?mission .
  ?incident sf:producesIncidentData ?dataset.
  ?dataset sf:containsDetection ?detection.
  ?detection sf:hasLocation ?location.
  ?location sf:hasLatitude ?lat.
  ?location sf:hasLongitude ?log.
  ?detection sf:hasDetectionFire true.
}

```

7 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented ONTO-SAFE, a framework that delivers a holistic, all-around model for semantically representing: (a) relevant incidents and impacts in a wildfire disaster and associated weather conditions, (b) data coming from human and earth observations, and, (c) missions and relationships between the services. The paper also presented how the proposed ontology satisfies the requirements of the end users through the demonstration of an ontology-based reasoning module for the management of a wildfire event. For future work, further research will focus on reasoning techniques that will be deployed on top of the ontology to support the decision-making process. Finally, the semantic reasoning module will be tested and validated in four pilots in for different forest fire areas and the reasoning outcomes will be evaluated in the field.

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